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The Origin of Chief Executive Officers and Performance in Hybrid Businesses: The Case of Microfinance

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This study examines the relationship between the origin of chief executive officers and performance in hybrid businesses using a sample of 353 microfinance institutions from 76 countries during 1996–2011. The statistical results suggest that microfinance institutions whose chief executive officers have been recruited internally perform better compared to institutions with externally-hired chief executive officers. The findings are consistent with the view that insider chief executive officers have firm-specific skills, experience and network resources that result in enhanced performance in hybrid businesses. Therefore, boards of microfinance institutions searching for a new chief executive officer should look for suitable internal candidates.

Introduction

Chief executive officers (CEOs) can be promoted from within a company or they can be recruited from outside – i.e. from other companies or organizations. The impact of a CEO's origin on commercial banks and other for-profit companies has been quite extensively analyzed in management literature (Ma, Seidl, and Guerard 2015) and the main question of interest is whether an association between a CEO's origin and a firm's performance can be documented. In this study we turn to microfinance institutions (MFIs), which are typical examples of hybrid businesses, having social goals alongside financial goals (Armendariz, and Morduch 2010; Hahn, and Ince 2016). Because of their dual nature, the management of hybrid businesses is particularly challenging (Battilana, and Dorado 2010).

Hybrid organizations are potentially very different from profit-maximizing corporations making it difficult, and maybe even impossible, to extend findings in the management literature from the latter to the former type of institutions. The literature examining the origin of CEOs and its effects on hybrid organizations' performance is, to the best of our knowledge, non-existent. This is unfortunate for hybrid businesses in general and particularly for the microfinance industry since there is a large and steadily growing demand for competent CEOs in a thin market for skilled labor where MFIs typically operate, (Randøy, Strøm, and Mersland 2015). Moreover, several studies argue that there is a need for more knowledge about factors influencing the efficiency of MFIs (see discussions in Mersland, and Strøm 2010; Pollinger, Outhwaite, and Cordero-Guzman 2007). After all, a major challenge for the microfinance industry is to make small and medium-sized MFIs financial sustainable in the long run (Hermes, and Lensink 2011).

A general contention in the microfinance literature is that access to financial services can contribute to reducing poverty. However, for the fight against poverty to be successful, it is a pre-requisite that MFIs are financial sustainable and cost-efficient (Mersland, and Strøm 2010).

Therefore, from both a financial and social perspective, possible CEO origin effects on financial performance are of potentially considerable importance. Similar to Adams, Almeida, and Ferreira (2005), and Galema, Lensink, and Mersland (2012), we argue that managers of MFIs have substantial managerial discretion, and the importance of CEO origin influence on performance is reinforced by the tremendous growth of the microfinance sector over the past years (Reed 2014). Given the newness of the industry, the high share of MFIs still managed by their founders and the fact that there is still untapped market potential of several billion poor customers who do not have access to financial services (Demirguc-Kunt, and Klapper 2012), the recruitment challenge is expected to become even more significant in the years to come. Thus, our study is timely.

In general, several unique aspects of hybrid businesses, and in particular MFIs, make the relation between performance and CEO characteristics an important research question. Thus far studies have focused on, for example, CEOs' founder status (Randøy, et al. 2015), gender status (Strøm, D'Espallier and Mersland, 2014; Périlleux, and Szafarz 2015), and CEO–board chair duality status (Galema, et al. 2012). One particularly interesting aspect of microfinance is the lack of powerful boards and, in general, weak monitoring of MFIs (Galema, et al. 2012). This potentially makes the CEOs of MFIs more influential than other CEOs. Moreover, according to Randøy, et al. (2015), CEOs in hybrid businesses like MFIs fit the characteristics of motivated agents (Besley, and Ghatak 2005), and such mission–driven agents could be motivated less by monetary incentives than other CEOs (Deutsch, Keil, and Laamanen 2011). Overall, it can be argued that if CEOs are more powerful in hybrid businesses and less influenced by traditional incentive mechanisms, the recruitment process becomes even more important in such entities than in conventional for profit companies.

In this study, we document significantly higher financial performance and better cost efficiency levels for MFIs managed by internally recruited CEOs compared to MFIs operated by CEOs hired from outside the organization. Moreover, MFIs managed by internally recruited CEOs appear to be associated with a lower level of performance variability. Thus, they are associated with lower risk since they deliver more stable financial results. We believe the results are interesting for hybrid businesses in general and particularly for the microfinance industry characterized by a thin labour market for CEOs (Randøy, et al. 2015) and a general lack of managerial capacity (CSFI 2011; 2014).

The paper proceeds as follows. Section two presents the background, prior research and hypotheses development. Section three introduces the research design and data sample and Section four presents the results, analysis, and discussion. Section five concludes the study.

Background, prior research and hypotheses development

The microfinance context

Hybrid organizations are widespread, and microfinance is only one among many industries with multiple objectives. However, the large size and extensive geographical outreach of the industry, combined with good access to high-quality and objective data (see data section below), make microfinance a particularly interesting setting for our research question. MFIs are financial institutions similar in many aspects to commercial banks, however there is a notable difference in the way they pursue their objectives. While the commercial banks work toward implementing one main objective of maximizing profits, MFIs work with two equally imperative objectives of banking and development (Battilana, and Dorado 2010; Hahn, and Ince 2016). The banking objective demands the provision of financial services in a manner that ensures financial sustainability of the MFI as an entity, to achieve profit or break-even from its operations. The

development objective aims at providing financial services in a manner that reduces poor peoples' economic hardship.

In the microfinance industry, CEO characteristics may have a more direct effect on performance than in other industries. The fragmented ownership and weak governance of most MFIs offer a limited role for investors to monitor and control the management (Mersland 2009). And while some MFIs are regulated and integrated into the formal financial sector, the majority are incorporated as Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) (Armendariz, and Morduch 2010; Yunus 1999). Therefore, the market for mergers and acquisitions in the microfinance industry that might offer an external control mechanism on microfinance management is immature or even totally absent.

An analysis of CEO origin in the microfinance industry should contribute to a broader understanding of how internal versus external recruitment might impact performance in an environment characterized by both weak governance and weak institutions for regulating its market (Chung, and Luo 2013). In a normally thin labor market for CEO candidates with higher and relevant education, a particularly relevant research question is whether work experience from within the firm can compensate for less-developed formal skills. The management literature in the microfinance industry is scarce. As stated by Galema, et al. (2012) this lack of research is unfortunate because 'MFIs serve hundreds of millions of poor and vulnerable people' (p. 718); research that can contribute to improving the management of MFIs may directly affect the MFIs' performance in terms of sustainability and impact on poverty reduction.

Literature review and hypotheses development

Existing studies on the performance consequences of the CEO origin are well documented for commercial banks and publicly-traded firms (Ma, et al. 2015). Empirical evidence from

previous studies found that inside CEOs' understanding of firms' capabilities pave a way to implementing strategies that positively influence the performance of firms (Lauterbach, Vu, and Weisberg 1999; Zajac 1990; Zhang, and Rajagopalan 2010). The literature indicates that, relative to outside CEOs, an internally recruited CEO is more knowledgeable about a firm's products line, its rivals in the markets, markets for products, clients, and its capacity to deliver products to clients (Chung, Rogers, Lubatkin, and Owers 1987). The knowledge and skills of the inside CEO are deep-rooted in the firm's existing resources (Karaevli, and Zajac 2013).

However, literature both in governance and management indicate that the effects of CEO characteristics (in this case internal versus external recruitment) on the performance of firms could be industry specific (Adams, and Mehran 2003; Rajagopalan, and Datta 1996). We follow this line of argument and propose that managers drawn to work in the microfinance industry and eventually internally promoted to the CEO position are strongly motivated agents (Besley, and Ghatak 2005). If the CEOs of the microfinance industry fit the definition of motivated agents, their personal preferences can be expected to be a better match with the dual objectives of banking and development upheld in the microfinance industry.

Empirical evidence in microfinance supports the contention that CEOs are motivated agents 'driven by nonmaterial motives' (Hahn, and Ince 2016, p. 33). Prior research suggests that MFIs in which the CEO is also the founder have better performance (Randøy, et al. 2015). Similarly to the founder-CEO, an internally recruited CEO also spends a considerable amount of time in the organization as the survivor of the 'internal corporate governance process [that promote managers] through the corporate hierarchy' (Anand, and Thakor 2008, p. 2738). This survival of an inside CEO enables him or her to secure support and deeper information through well-established social networks with board members, employees in the lower cadre, clients, and

other stakeholders (Chung, et al. 1987). Using internal firm-specific know-how and their prior exposure to the firm resources, inside CEOs could be better able to interpret the firm's complex business information (Chung, et al. 1987; Hambrick, and Mason 1984).

Based on the assumption that inside CEOs in the microfinance industry fit the characteristic of motivated agents, we expect that inside CEOs are less likely to engage in projects that are value destroying. In more general terms, we expect that the productivity of mission-driven organizations, like MFIs, is higher when there is a good match between mission and employees (Besley, and Ghatak 2005), and we hypothesize a positive association between internally recruited CEOs and MFIs' financial performance. As metrics for financial performance, we apply return on assets (ROA) and operational costs (more on this below).

Notably, we cannot completely rule out the possibility that the relation between origin and performance may be the opposite of what we suggest. Contrary to positive consequences, overconfidence of the internally promoted CEOs could also weaken the internal corporate governance mechanisms (for example, monitoring by boards of directors) and, thus, increase his or her entrenchment (Anand, and Thakor 2008; Engelen, Neumann, and Schwens 2015). As a result, an inside CEO could implement value destroying projects or increase perks (Anand, and Thakor 2008), and thus have a negative effect on the MFI performance.

Our second hypothesis is on risk, or to be more specific, performance variability. Because most MFIs are not listed, no market-based risk proxy (such as the variability of stock returns) can be applied in this part of the study. We follow previous microfinance studies (Galema, et al. 2012), and measure performance variability as the variability of ROA and operational costs. Prior research suggests that such measures are meaningful in the microfinance industry. For instance, Beisland, and Mersland (2013) document significant differences in the variability of accounting

returns between NGOs on the one hand and cooperatives and credit unions on the other. Although their analysis is not related to CEO origin, the study instructively illustrates that there may be systematic differences in risk between different MFIs, for instance based on differences in governance structures or managerial discretion and competence.

Using the variability of ROA as their risk metric, Galema, et al. (2012) investigate risk-taking in MFIs in relation to CEO power. They find that risk is positively associated with CEO power. It is argued that more power induces CEOs to make more extreme decisions that increase risk. One may argue that internally recruited CEOs have a better internal network and, hence, are more powerful. If so, one would expect to document higher risk for MFIs headed by inside CEOs, based on Galema, et al. (2012). This line of reasoning is consistent with a study of Zhang, and Rajagopalan (2010) which argues that internally promoted CEOs are likely to amplify a firm's organizational slack and eventually increase risk taking.

On the other hand, consistent with the arguments presented about an inside CEO being more skilled, in general, compared to external hires (Chung, et al. 1987), the inside CEO should be better at avoiding bad decisions on the MFI's behalf. Thus, if an inside CEO is simply more competent, this should materialize in not only improved performance levels, but also lower risk levels, that is lower performance variability. Moreover, given that inside CEOs are motivated agents, one could expect that these CEOs are characterized by a genuine desire to do good and contribute to poverty reduction in poor segments. Such social concerns may reduce the possibility that the CEO gambles with the long-term financial survival of the MFI. Thus, also from this line of reasoning, an inside CEO may be expected to be associated with lower risk-taking within the MFI.

For both hypotheses, prior research is ambiguous and we cannot completely rule out the possibility that the relation may be the opposite of what we suggest. Therefore, all tests are two-sided. Our hypotheses can be summarized as follows;

Hypothesis 1a (H1a): MFIs with internally recruited CEOs have higher ROA than MFIs with externally recruited CEOs.

Hypothesis 1b (H1b): MFIs with internally recruited CEOs have lower operational costs than MFIs with externally recruited CEOs.

Hypothesis 2 (H2): Internally recruited CEOs are more risk-averse with the result that MFIs with internally recruited CEOs have lower variability of ROA and operational costs.

Given that MFIs offer financial services to poor people in developing and emerging countries, a contention in the microfinance literature is that microfinance services contribute to the fight against poverty - the social performance objective of MFIs. In this study, we use data from MFIs that are rated by third party rating agencies. This type of MFIs is to a large extent financed by donations and subsidized loans provided by so-called 'impact investors' (Hudon, and Traca 2011). The social performance dimension is therefore implicit in our data. Moreover, it is being argued that MFIs need to focus more on their financial performance, and in particular on their costs, if they are to be able to produce social results in the longer run (Mersland, and Strøm 2010). After all, only MFIs operating with low costs are able to service small loans, which are costly, at reasonably priced interest rate levels (Mersland, and Strøm 2010). Thus, focusing on financial performance, and in particular on the MFI's operating costs, is relevant also for its

social performance. The question of whether CEO-origin may affect other dimensions of social performance is left for future research.

Data sample, research design and descriptive statistics

Data sample

The sample consists of data from MFI rating agencies. Specifically, the data have been collected from rating reports by the rating agencies MicroRate, Microfinanza, Planet rating, Crisil and M-Cril; these are well-known top rating agencies in the microfinance industry and were originally approved by the Rating Fund of the Consultative Group to Assist the Poor (CGAP) (Gutiérrez-Nieto, and Serrano-Cinca 2007). In the rating reports, information on governance, management, financial performance, and operations is available.

Big commercial banks offering microfinance services are not to be considered hybrid organizations and are therefore excluded from the analysis. Similarly, time-limited development projects without a business focus are excluded. The sample includes small and medium-sized MFIs, which are the typical providers of microfinance services and that can be categorized as hybrid organizations. The MFIs of the sample have themselves chosen to become rated to improve their performance and access to funding. Thus, our sample selection criteria assure that particularly small or unprofessional MFIs are excluded from the sample.

A somewhat special attribute of the microfinance industry, because of its newness, is the relatively large proportion of MFIs still managed by their founders. Founder-CEOs, with their rather unique characteristics and motivations (Randøy, et al. 2015), do not fit well in a study focusing on the differences between internally and externally hired CEOs. Moreover, since the industry is maturing and our main purpose is to make a contribution to the recruitment process of MFIs, MFIs still managed by their founders are simply excluded from the analysis. For a study

of the impact of founder-CEOs in the microfinance industry, we refer to (Randøy, et al. 2015). The final sample includes 353 MFIs from 76 countries during the 1996–2011 time period, of which 18% have internally recruited CEOs. Hence, internal hires for the CEO position in MFIs is not very common.

Research design

We start the empirical investigation with bivariate t–tests based on the CEO–origin. This descriptive analysis allows for an initial test on possible differences between MFI characteristics based on the CEO–origin, i.e., differences in financial performance including cost differences as well as other differences described by the control variables. However, no strong conclusions on our hypotheses are drawn based on these general tests; instead we proceed with a multivariate research design to test the proposed hypotheses. Multivariate empirical studies on CEO origin and its effects on MFIs’ performance face a familiar setback of omitted variable bias. To address such problems, researchers employ a within firm’s variation methodology (Kaplan, Klebanov, and Sorensen 2012; Malmendier, Tate, and Yan 2011). Consistent with prior research (cf. Kaplan, et al. 2012), we conduct a test for the influence of CEO–origin on MFIs performance using the following general fixed effects (within) regression equation.

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + x'_{it}\beta + v_{it} \tag{1}$$

Where; $i = 1, \dots, N$ MFIs; $t = 1, \dots, T$ time periods;

y_{it} represent the performance metrics (ROA and operational costs)

x'_{it} is a vector of explanatory variables, both the test variable (CEO = insider) and control variables

v_{it} represent the error term

α_i represent a time invariant unobserved firm effects

In contrast to the t-tests, the multivariate analysis captures the time-dimension of our dataset (more on this later).

ROA is our first dependent variable to proxy for MFIs' financial performance. ROA is the most commonly used financial performance metric of the microfinance industry (Galema, et al. 2012) and it is also frequently applied in banking studies (Ma, et al. 2015). Since equity levels differ widely among MFIs ROA is considered to be a better benchmark than ROE when studying the performance of MFIs (Mersland and Strøm, 2009). Since our panel data sample is drawn from multiple countries, we follow Mersland, and Strøm (2009) and adjust ROA for differences in country inflation.

In addition to ROA we use operational costs (scaled by total loan portfolio) as our second financial performance metric. Because operational costs are not affected by revenue, we regard this variable as a reasonable proxy for cost–efficiency in MFIs (Randøy, et al. 2015). Moreover, as mentioned above, cost efficiency is a precondition to service small loans and perform well on the MFI's social dimension (Mersland and Strøm, 2010). Notably, operational costs are skewed to the right and we apply a logarithm transformation of this variable in all statistical tests. ROA and operational costs are related but cover different aspects of financial performance; MFIs can have high ROA but still be cost-inefficient, or they can be cost-efficient without having high ROA (because ROA is affected by revenue). In particular, since MFIs often operate in markets with low competition (McIntosh, and Wydick 2005) they can easily forward high operational costs to their clients in the form of high interest rates (Rosenberg, Gaul, Ford, and Tomilova 2013). Thus, the inclusion of operational costs alongside ROA is a strength of our

study; to the extent that results from the two specifications are comparable, the robustness of any conclusion drawn in this study is strengthened.

Similar to previous studies on CEO origin (Zhang, and Rajagopalan 2010), we apply a binary indicator variable for internal versus external recruitment as our test variable. Specifically, CEO=Insider equals one when the CEO is recruited from within the firm, and is zero otherwise. Firm performance can obviously be related to a number of MFI attributes besides CEO characteristics, and hence we use an extensive set of control variables (selected based on prior studies, see Galema, et al. 2012; Randøy, et al. 2015). We use five categories of control variables. Similarly to operational cost, we follow a procedure of applying a logarithm transformation to any control variable that is right skewed (Box, and Cox 1964; Emerson, and Stoto 1983). *First*, we control for the MFI market focus and mission using the natural logarithm of average loan size and a binary variable for urban versus rural lending market focus; MFIs' profitability and cost can obviously be influenced by the market type and the size of a loan an MFI decides to provide. *Second*, corporate governance mechanisms such as bank regulations, debt holders' monitoring (measured as leverage), the percentage of stakeholders on board, and international board members sitting on board are likely to differ across MFIs. Such differences in governance structures can influence financial performance and need to be controlled for. *Third*, the MFI's size (measured as the natural logarithm of total assets), geographical expansion (measured as branch offices), and the MFI's organizational form (Bank, Non-bank financial institution, Non-governmental organization, and credit/cooperative union) can be related to the MFI's profitability as well as its cost structure. For example, larger MFIs could enjoy economies of scale, hence, better performance. *Fourth*, the number of years of experience of operation as MFIs could provide an added advantage for the MFI for a decision such as cost cutting. *Fifth* we use

the Human Development Index (HDI) to control for country-specific differences regarding health, education and income (GDP per capita). In Table 1 we list the definitions of all variables applied in this study.

In the second part of the study, we extend the performance analysis to also include performance variability/risk. We start with a simple F-test, a robust variance F-statistics according to Brown, and Forsythe (1974). We test whether the standard deviation of ROA and operational costs differs by the CEO origin status. Then we proceed with a multivariate research design, where we examine the association between the inside CEO-variable with MFI performance variability over time. Such an approach is also applied in other studies that investigate the influence of CEOs on the variability of firm performance (Adams, et al. 2005; Galema, et al. 2012). *First*, we compute the standard deviation of our two measures of MFI performance, namely ROA and operational costs. *Second*, we compute the average of the CEO = Insider_{*i*} and Controls_{*it*} over time. Thereafter, we regress the respective standard deviation Std.Dev(MFI performance)_{*i*} (one per MFI) on the averages of our independent variables $\overline{CEO = Insider}_i$ and $\overline{Controls}_i$;

$$Std.Dev(MFI performance)_i = \varphi_1 + \varphi_2 \overline{CEO = Insider}_i + \varphi_3 \overline{Controls}_i + \mu_i \quad (2)$$

Table 1
Measurements and definitions of variables

Variable	Definition
Dependent variable	
Return on assets (ROA)	Net operating income/Average operational assets
ln(Operational costs)	The natural logarithm of (Operating expenses/Loan portfolio)
Independent variable	
CEO=Insider	A binary variable set equal to one if the current CEO was an employee in the firm, and zero otherwise
Control variables	
ln(Average loan size)	The natural logarithm of (Loan portfolio/Number of Active credit clients)

Urban lending Regulation	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI market focus is urban, and zero otherwise
Leverage	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI is regulated by the country's banking authority, and zero otherwise
Stakeholders on board	The ratio of the total debts to total assets
International board members	$[\text{Employee directors} + \text{Donor directors} + \text{Client directors}]/\text{Total number of board members}$
ln(Total assets)	Total numbers of directors on board with foreign background
Branch offices	The natural logarithm of total assets
Bank	Number of branch offices
Non-Bank Financial Institution	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI is organized as a commercial bank, and zero otherwise
Non-Governmental organization	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI is organized as an NBFI, and zero otherwise
Credit Union/Cooperative	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI is organized as an NGO, and zero otherwise
MFI age	A binary variable set equal to one if the MFI type is a Credit Union/Cooperative, and zero otherwise
Human Development Index	Total number of years of operation as an MFI
	A ranking for each country covering health, education and income GDP per capita

Note: Leverage is computed as the ratio of $[\text{debt} + \text{voluntary savings}]/\text{total assets}$. Inclusion of the voluntary deposits in the total debts takes into account the banking nature of MFIs. The ROA in the regression is adjusted for the country's inflation using the $[\text{ROA} - \text{Inflation}]/[1 + \text{Inflation}]$ formula (Mersland, and Strøm 2009).

Descriptive statistics

In Table 2, we present the summary statistics for dependent, independent and control variables. We note that ROA on average is two percent, which confirms the general low profitability observed in the microfinance industry (Hermes, and Lensink, 2011). Operational cost is 27 percent of the loan portfolio on average which is very high compared to regular banks, reflecting the high cost involved in lending small amounts without formal collateral (Mersland and Strøm, 2010). Most CEOs are recruited externally, in our sample only 18 percent of the CEOs are recruited from within the MFI. A national banking authority regulates 30 percent of the MFIs, and 20 percent of the MFIs have their main market focus on urban areas.

Five percent of the MFIs are organized as banks, 29 percent as Non-bank financial institutions, 51 percent as a Non-governmental establishment, and 15 percent are organized as cooperatives/credit unions. The cooperatives/credit unions are excluded from the multivariate analysis to avoid perfect multicollinearity and thus functions as the reference category in the

regressions. Regarding board characteristics, about 15 percent of the members represent stakeholders. There are only 0.3 international board members on average, but the spread is huge; the maximum number of board members with a foreign background is seven in our sample. The MFI age in our sample on average is 12 years. 52 percent of the total assets of the sample are financed with debts, and the average total assets are US \$11 million. The average loan size is USD 790. On average, an MFI in the sample has 13 branch offices, and the average Human Development Index is 61 percent, confirming that most MFIs are situated in relatively poor countries.

Table 2
Summary statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Dependent variables					
Return on assets (ROA)	1447	0.02	0.11	-0.95	0.56
Operational costs	1344	0.27	0.17	0.02	0.99
ln(operational costs)	1344	0.23	0.12	0.02	0.69
Independent test variable					
Inside CEO	1304	0.18	0.38	0.00	1.00
Control variables					
Average loan size	2142	790.33	1388.18	1.25	24588.60
ln(average loan size)	2142	5.99	1.21	0.23	10.11
Urban lending	1861	0.20	0.40	0.00	1.00
Regulation	2078	0.30	0.46	0.00	1.00
Leverage	1592	0.52	0.21	0.05	0.80
Stakeholders on board	806	0.15	0.33	0.00	1.00
International board members	1290	0.30	0.99	0.00	7.00
Total assets	2249	11.3	24.6	0.02	279
ln(Total assets)	2249	15.14	1.50	9.87	19.45
Branch office	1171	13.50	16.61	1.00	129.00
Banks	2127	0.05	0.22	0.00	1.00
Non-Bank Financial Institution	2127	0.29	0.45	0.00	1.00
Non-Governmental Organizations	2127	0.51	0.50	0.00	1.00
Credit union/Cooperatives	2127	0.15	0.35	0.00	1.00
MFI age	2169	11.96	8.74	1.00	80.00
Human development index (HDI)	1642	0.61	0.14	0.05	0.81

Note: In Table 2, the values of Total assets are in million US\$ dollar. The average loan size is in US\$ dollar.

In Table 3, we report correlations between explanatory variables. The correlations are generally low and below recommended cut-off points, for example 0.6 (Hair, Tatham, Anderson, and Black 2006). Furthermore, a test of variance inflations factor (results not shown) suggest that the investigation may proceed without serious concerns about multicollinearity.

Table 3
Correlations

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
(1)Inside CEO	1	0.00	0.16	-0.01	-0.15	0.04	0.03	0.10	0.04	0.01	-0.10	0.12	0.05	0.03
(2)ln(average loan size)		1	0.10	0.02	0.23	0.09	0.25	0.12	0.02	0.24	0.36	-0.49	-0.09	-0.28
(3)Urban lending			1	0.13	-0.08	-0.03	0.16	0.11	-0.01	0.06	0.03	0.01	-0.04	0.12
(4)Regulation				1	0.05	0.06	-0.10	0.09	0.19	0.07	-0.17	-0.20	0.03	-0.02
(5)Leverage					1	0.03	-0.06	-0.20	0.21	0.01	-0.10	-0.63	-0.29	-0.14
(6)Stakeholders percentage on board						1	-0.16	-0.15	-0.21	-0.11	-0.01	0.07	0.14	0.25
(7)International board members							1	0.23	0.20	0.00	0.00	-0.06	0.15	0.03
(8)ln(Total assets)								1	0.11	-0.04	0.21	-0.08	-0.16	0.03
(9)Branch office									1	0.15	0.09	0.37	0.13	0.04
(10)Banks										1	0.12	0.04	0.04	-0.12
(11) Non-Bank Financial Institution											1	0.40	0.33	0.03
(12) Non-Governmental Organizations												1	-0.19	0.12
(13)MFI age													1	-0.19
(14)Human development index														1

Note: Table 3 correlations among variables reflect only observations for which there is no missing value.

Results, analysis, and discussion

Initial analysis: MFIs characteristics based on the CEO origin

The initial analysis examines whether there are differences in MFI characteristics based on the CEO origin using a mean comparison t-test. In Table 4, we observe that the average ROA in MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider (0.037) is higher than the ROA reported by MFIs in which the CEO is an outsider (0.010), and the difference in mean is significant at $p < 0.01$. Likewise, the average operational costs in MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider (0.256) is lower than that of MFIs in which the CEO is an outsider (0.283), and the difference in mean is significant at $p < 0.01$.

Table 4
Mean comparison t-tests

CEO origin status	CEO≠Insider	CEO=Insider	Difference in means
Variables	Mean [Std. Dev.]	Mean[Std. Dev.]	[p-value]
Return on assets (ROA)	0.010[0.113]	0.037[0.102]	-0.027[0.000]
Operational costs	0.283[0.177]	0.256[0.142]	0.027[0.007]
Average loan size	835.330[1577.236]	706.724[745.530]	128.605 [0.055]
Urban lending	0.068[0.253]	0.065[0.246]	0.04 [0.428]
Regulations	0.314[0.464]	0.310[0.463]	-0.004 [0.459]
Leverage	0.662[0.410]	0.541[0.257]	0.120[0.000]
Stakeholders on board	0.162[0.344]	0.187[0.375]	-0.025 [0.235]
International board members	0.260[0.915]	0.539[1.150]	-0.279 [0.002]
Total assets	11.3[26.6]	19.8[38.500]	-8.52 [0.004]
Branch offices	8.794[19.496]	15.523[18.200]	-6.729 [0.000]
MFI age	11.502[8.677]	13.561[9.319]	-2.059 [0.006]

Note: In Table 4, we report t-tests for equality of means between MFIs in which the CEO is an insider and MFIs in which the CEO is recruited externally.

We also observe considerable differences between MFIs with an inside CEO compared to an outside CEO on several of the control variables. In Table 4, we note that MFIs with insider CEO have significantly smaller average loan size, more branches and lower leverage compared to MFIs managed by an outsider. Insider managed MFIs are also significantly larger than MFIs managed by externally hired CEOs.

Overall, the initial test on performance level supports the first hypothesis; MFIs with internally recruited CEOs appear to have higher ROA and lower operational costs than MFIs with

externally recruited CEOs. However, we identify many other systematic differences between the two sets of MFIs. Thus, the differences in performance might be explained by other characteristics than CEO origin and, as stated above, we await the multivariate analysis before drawing strong conclusions.

We conclude this subsection with an initial analysis on possible differences in performance variability based on CEO origin. In Table 5, we report robust variance F–tests on equality of performance variability.

Table 5
Robust variance F–tests of equality of performance variances

Robust test for equality of return on assets (ROA) variances	
CEO≠Insider (Std. Dev.)	0.113
Number of observations	1029
CEO=Insider (Std. Dev.)	0.102
Number of observations	221
Variance F–test [p–value]	10.370[0.001]
Robust test for equality of operational cost variances	
CEO≠Insider (Std. Dev.)	0.177
Number of observations	1050
CEO=Insider (Std. Dev.)	0.142
Number of observations	226
Variance F–test [p–value]	8.656 [0.003]

Note: In Table 5, we report robust variance F–statistics of Brown and Forsythe (1974). We test whether the variance of ROA and operational costs differs by the CEO origin status.

We test whether the variance of ROA and operational costs differs by the CEO origin status. The standard deviation of the ROA in MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider is 0.102. The comparable standard deviation for externally recruited CEOs is 0.113, and the F–test is significant at $p < 0.01$. MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider have lower standard deviation of operational costs (0.142) than those with outside CEOs (0.177), and the F–test is significant at $p < 0.01$. Hence, the results uphold that the variances of ROA and operational costs differ by the CEO origin status. However, once again, we await the multivariate analysis before drawing conclusions.

Multivariate results

In Table 6 we report the results on the inside CEO–variable and its association with the MFIs’ ROA, and operational costs. In Model 1 and Model 3, we examine the association without control variables. In Model 2 and Model 4, we add control variables successively. Thus, we test the stability of our results for different regression specifications. Moreover, because the number of observations varies for the control variables, the expansions of the regression model are also a test of the stability across different subsets of our sample.

The coefficient of the inside CEO on ROA is positive and significant for all specifications suggesting that MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider have a higher ROA, consistent with Hypothesis 1a and in line with what Zajac (1990) and Zhang, and Rajagopalan (2010) have found for publicly–traded firms in the U.S. Some of the control variables in Model 2 turn out to be significant. In particular, and in line with Mori, and Mersland (2014) the coefficient of the percentage of stakeholders on the MFI’s board is positive and significant, indicating that the presence of employee, client and donor directors improves ROA. Moreover, MFI–size as measured by total assets has a positive association with ROA which is in line with Hartarska, Shen, and Mersland (2013).

However, geographical expansion in the form of more branches appears to affect the profitability negatively; more branches may lead to lower productivity, relatively speaking. Thus, size is an ambiguous explanatory variable for financial performance. The coefficient of the average loan size on ROA is negative and significant indicating that providing small loans in a profitable manner is difficult (D’Espallier, Hudon, and Szafarz 2016; Hermes, and Lensink 2007) and underlining the importance of MFIs to be cost efficient (Mersland, and Strøm 2010).

Furthermore, the results in Model 4 indicate that MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider have lower operational costs; hence, the results support Hypothesis 1b. The results can be related

to the findings of Bornemann, Kick, Pfungsten, and Schertler (2015). These researchers find evidence that banks in which the incoming CEO is an outsider have higher discretionary expenses than banks with an insider CEO.

Table 6**Panel–data estimation, fixed effects (within) regression: Inside CEO and their effects on MFIs performance**

Dependent variable Independent variables	Return on assets (ROA)				Operational costs			
	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
Inside CEO	0.039**	(0.020)	0.076**	(0.034)	-0.144*	(0.078)	-0.276**	(0.131)
ln(average loan size)			-0.067**	(0.030)			0.018	(0.051)
Urban Lending			-0.010	(0.026)			0.053	(0.060)
Regulation			0.040	(0.030)			-0.134	(0.111)
Leverage			-0.045	(0.048)			-0.017	(0.103)
Stakeholders percentage on board			0.076*	(0.043)			0.024	(0.173)
International board members			0.008	(0.016)			-0.043	(0.060)
ln(Total assets)			0.064***	(0.024)			-0.137**	(0.064)
Branch office			-0.002***	(0.001)			-0.001	(0.002)
Bank			0.047	(0.083)			0.312***	(0.056)
Non–Bank Financial Institutions			-0.016	(0.089)			0.290***	(0.097)
Non–Governmental Organizations			0.033	(0.092)			0.339***	(0.102)
MFI age			-0.002	(0.032)			-0.003	(0.098)
Human development index			-0.065	(0.047)			0.210	(0.281)
Constant	-0.047***	(0.003)	-0.538	(0.403)	-1.223***	(0.011)	0.554	(1.099)
Time dummies	No		Yes		No		Yes	
Observations	1,074		647		853		515	
R–squared	0.009		0.165		0.016		0.244	
Number of MFIs	427		319		361		265	
p–value(F)	0.001		0.000		0.016		0.000	

Note: In Table 6, we report coefficients and in parentheses are Standard Errors clustered at the MFI level. Operational costs=ln(Operational costs)

***, **, and * denote 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 significance level

Similarly, in Model 4, we find a size effect; larger MFIs as measured by total assets appear to enjoy economies of scale (Hartarska, et al. 2013). However, the negative effect of geographical expansion disappears in Model 4. Thus, the positive size effect appears to be more robust than the negative effect of more branches suggested by the previous analysis. Finally, we note that cooperatives and credit unions (the MFI-category that was left out) have significantly lower operational costs than other MFI types.

The positive effects on ROA and operational costs for insider-CEOs suggests that their experience and skills are deep-rooted on the existing MFI's capabilities (Karaevli, and Zajac 2013). Understanding an MFI's capability seems to pave a way for an inside CEO to implement strategies with a positive influence on financial performance (Zhang, and Rajagopalan 2010). Similarly, an inside CEO is a survivor of the 'internal corporate governance process [that promote managers] through the corporate hierarchy' (Anand, and Thakor 2008), and, moreover, we argue that inside CEOs fit the characteristics of motivated agents (cf. Randøy, et al. 2015). Overall, the results we observe suggest that MFIs in which the CEO is internally promoted are more profitable and cost-efficient, relatively speaking.

To check the sensitivity of our results on Hypothesis 1 we examine the effect of inside CEO on MFI ROA and operational costs using a one-step system GMM, an instrumental variable approach. The results are reported in the Appendix, see Table A1. The results we observe in Table A1 are similar to those observed in Table 6. Because the methodology of Table A1 is better suited for addressing possible endogeneity, these results suggest that we observe a causal relation and not only a statistical association.

Performance variability analysis

In Table 7, we report results from the pooled cross-sectional regressions for the standard deviation of ROA and operational costs as the function of the inside CEO variable and control

variables. As before, we include explanatory variables successively. In Model 1 and Model 3, we include the inside CEO variable only, and in Model 2 and Model 4 we include all other control variables. In Model 2, the coefficient of inside CEO is negative and significant. The results suggest that there is a negative association between inside CEOs and the standard deviation of ROA. Likewise, in Model 4, the coefficient of inside CEO is negative (although only weakly significant), indicating that inside CEOs have lower standard deviations for operational costs than those recruited externally.

We note that few of the control variables show up as significant in these regressions, in particular when operational costs are studied. For the variability of ROA, it is notable that the increased presence of stakeholders on board is associated with a higher standard deviation of ROA. Thus, it appears that such board members contribute to increased risk taking in MFIs. Moreover, we note that more branch offices increase the risk as measured by the variability of ROA. As for MFI-type, cooperatives and credit unions (the left-out category in the regressions) have lower risk than banks, non-bank financial institutions and NGOs. In the regressions using the standard deviation of operational cost as the dependent variable, only international board members show up as a significant variable. Thus, presence of international players appears to increase risk taking as measured by operational cost variability.

Given that very little research has been conducted on risk differences in hybrid businesses, this second part of our study is rather novel. Nonetheless, our results are consistent in the sense that they all support the second hypothesis of lower risk taking among internally recruited CEOs. The lower risk taking can be skills-related or it can be due to the fact that CEOs may be motivated agents. For instance, it may be that inside CEOs, with their experience from the industry and organization, are better at evaluating risk relative to reward for new projects or products. Or it may be that their motivation for helping poor people puts a ceiling on risk taking. We cannot separate the first plausible explanation from the second. Note that risk taking is not necessarily negative *per se*; firms increase risk to improve financial performance. Keeping this fact in mind, it is interesting to note that even though inside CEOs appear to be associated with less risk, these managers are also associated with better financial performance. The extra risk taking of external CEOs does not seem to materialize in improved financial performance. A word of caution is needed: given that this research is still in its infancy, it could be that some underlying variable left out of our analysis contributes to explaining the findings. Moreover, risk taking might have positive effects on the second component of MFIs' dual objectives, the social performance. For instance, new products or markets may increase outreach to poor clients. This issue is, however, left for future research.

Table 7
Pooled Cross-sectional regressions: Standard deviation of performance as the function of inside CEO

Dependent variables	Standard deviation return on assets (ROA)				Standard deviation operational costs			
Independent variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
Inside CEO	-0.006*	(0.003)	-0.010***	(0.004)	-0.005*	(0.003)	-0.006*	(0.003)
ln(average loan size)			0.000	(0.002)			-0.001	(0.001)
Urban lending			0.003	(0.003)			-0.002	(0.003)
Regulation			-0.000	(0.003)			0.004	(0.003)
Leverage			-0.000	(0.001)			0.001	(0.002)
Stakeholders on board			0.011**	(0.005)			-0.004	(0.004)
International board members			-0.001	(0.001)			0.003***	(0.001)
ln(Total assets)			-0.001	(0.001)			-0.000	(0.001)
Branch office			0.000**	(0.000)			-0.000	(0.000)
Bank			0.021***	(0.008)			-0.013	(0.008)
Non-bank financial institutions			0.009*	(0.005)			-0.005	(0.005)
Non-Governmental organisation			0.011**	(0.005)			0.004	(0.005)
MFI age			0.000	(0.000)			0.000	(0.000)
Human development index			-0.006	(0.006)			0.005	(0.004)
Constant	0.023***	(0.001)	0.009	(0.018)	0.019***	(0.001)	0.018	(0.016)
Time dummies	No		Yes		No		Yes	
Observations	309		241		296		229	
R-squared	0.014		0.197		0.015		0.249	
p-value (F-statistic)	0.096		0.000		0.081		0.000	

Note: In Table 7, we report coefficients and in parentheses are Standard Errors clustered at MFI level. We use equation $Std(performance)_i = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 \overline{CEO\ insider}_i + \gamma_3 \overline{Controls}_i + \mu_i$ to run each of the model.

***, **, and * denotes 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 significant level.

Conclusions

This study provides an initial examination of the impact of inside CEOs on MFIs' financial performance and risk taking. As far as we know this is the first attempt to study whether internally hired CEOs outperform externally hired CEOs in hybrid businesses. Our empirical evidence suggests that internal hires are indeed better. MFIs in which the CEO is also an insider have higher ROA and lower operational costs than MFIs with externally recruited CEOs. Moreover, the risk, as measured by the variability in respectively ROA and operational costs, appears to be lower when MFIs recruit CEOs internally. Our results are consistent with the view that inside CEOs are more knowledgeable about their firm's product lines; rivals in the markets; clients; and workforces' capability to deliver the products to the clients (Chung, et al. 1987; Wiklund, Nordqvist, Hellerstedt, and Bird 2013) which in hybrid businesses are probably more complex than in regular businesses.

Moreover, the performance effect we observe with insider CEOs reflects the motivational hypothesis, that is, their intrinsic motivation embedded within hybrid organizations' missions (Besley, and Ghatak 2005).. An interesting avenue for future research would be to investigate in detail the specific mechanisms and skills that cause the financial performance of internally recruited CEOs to outperform that of externally hired CEOs. In particular we believe that internally hired CEOs work better in hybrid businesses like MFIs because such are complex organizations requiring inside experience to understand the organization, the market and the interplay between the two. Moreover, we believe that motivated agent-type CEOs are associated with lower discretionary expenses.

The results are consistent across different tests and appear to be robust. Moreover, our findings suggest a causal relationship between CEO origin and performance, and not only a statistical association. The complex activities of hybrid organizations and the intrinsic motivations (to do good) of their managers might explain why internal recruitment can be even more effective in MFIs and other hybrid organizations than in other (for-profit) industries. Thus, our findings support the claim that the effects of CEO characteristics (in this case internal versus external recruitment) on the performance of firms is industry specific (Adams, and Mehran 2003; Rajagopalan, and Datta 1996).

Given that it is the board that de facto employs the top manager, future analysis should also address the (often complex) relationship between the boards and their CEOs. Research on the management of hybrid businesses is still in its infancy, thus future studies shedding light on managerial challenges related to operating with both social and financial objectives are definitely needed. Such studies should address possible conflicts between social and financial objectives on the CEO-level.

The practical implication of our study should be obvious; the boards of hybrid businesses, and in particular MFIs, should also look internally when searching for new candidates for the CEO position. The fact that less than one fifth of hired CEOs of MFIs are found internally signals a situation where boards probably do not put enough emphasis on the training of its middle managers and on appreciating knowledge that is accumulated internally.

We conclude the study with a caveat; because of its extensive geographical outreach, millions of clients and expected continued high growth (Demirguc-Kunt, and Klapper 2012), we

have chosen to use the microfinance industry as our case in this study of hybrid businesses. However, although many hybrid businesses – similar to MFIs - are categorized by high degrees of complexity, weak governance structures, and motivated-agent type CEOs, hybrid industries are heterogenous and potentially very different from each other. Therefore, our findings may not extend to all other hybrid industries. A fruitful avenue for future research might be to investigate how unique aspects of different hybrid industries influence the management, governance and performance of the various entities of the industries.

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Appendix

To address possible endogeneity in the tests of Hypothesis 1, we apply an instrumental variable approach as a robustness test (cf. Kaplan, et al. 2012). Similar to Bornemann, et al. (2015), we use the lagged dependent variable as our instrument (Roodman 2009). The applied performance proxies, test variable and control variables are identical to those used in the main analysis. The results of the supplementary test are reported in Table A1

Table A1
Panel–data estimation, One-step system GMM: inside CEOs and their effects on MFIs performance

Dependent variable	Return on assets (ROA)				Operational costs			
Independent variables	Model 1		Model 2		Model 3		Model 4	
Inside CEO	0.044***	(0.015)	0.075***	(0.028)	-0.126**	(0.059)	-0.108**	(0.054)
ln(Average loan size)			-0.067***	(0.020)			0.016	(0.034)
Urban Lending			-0.008	(0.014)			0.008	(0.029)
Regulation			0.031	(0.032)			-0.087***	(0.022)
Leverage			-0.045	(0.030)			0.019	(0.041)
Stakeholders percentage on board			0.065	(0.056)			-0.052	(0.072)
International board members			0.004	(0.018)			-0.144*	(0.075)
ln(Total assets)			0.063***	(0.018)			-0.141***	(0.029)
Branch office			-0.002**	(0.001)			-0.001	(0.001)
Bank			0.023	(0.086)			0.368***	(0.047)
Non–Bank Financial Institutions			-0.063	(0.160)			0.400***	(0.060)
Non–Governmental Organizations			-0.016	(0.165)			0.425***	(0.059)
MFI age			0.050	(0.168)			0.050	(0.082)
Human development index			-0.077	(0.062)			0.304**	(0.154)
ROA (lagged)			0.234	(0.271)				
Operational costs (Lagged)							0.093	(0.050)
Constant	-0.048***	(0.006)	-0.847	(0.962)	-1.226***	(0.031)	0.399	(0.592)
Time dummies	No		Yes		No		Yes	
Observations	1,074		647		853		515	
Number of MFIs	427		319		361		265	
p–value(F)	0.003		0.000		0.035		0.000	
Sargan test (p–value)	0.833		0.274		0.339		0.552	
AR(2) test (p–value)	0.350		0.134		0.244		0.258	

Note: In Table A1, we report coefficients and in parentheses are Standard Errors clustered at MFI level. Operational costs=ln(Operational costs). ***, **, and * denotes 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 significance level